

**PROFESSIONAL ETHICS AND MENTORSHIP AS CORRELATES
FOR SCHOOL LEADERS ENHANCEMENT OF NEW-ENTRANT
TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
AKWA IBOM STATE**

Love Effiong Ebuk Ph. D^{1*}, Idorenyin John Ekop²

*The authors declare
that no funding was
received for this work.*

Received: 01-December-2025

Accepted: 15-January-2025

Published: 20-February-2026

Copyright © 2026, Authors retain copyright. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> (CC BY 4.0 deed)

This article is published by **MSI Publishers** in **MSI Journal of Arts, Law and Justice (MSIJALJ)**
ISSN 3049-0839 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers

Volume: 3, Issue: 2 (February-2026)

^{1*}Department of Educational Management Faculty of Education Yakubu Gowon University (formerly known as University of Abuja).

²Department of Educational Management Faculty of Education Yakubu Gowon University (formerly known as University of Abuja).

* **Correspondence:** Love Effiong Ebuk Ph. D

ABSTRACT: The paper focused on professional ethics and mentorship as correlates for school leaders' enhancement of new entrant teachers' work performance in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The researchers set two research questions to guide the study. Survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 2,128 teachers and 376 principals from 376 public secondary schools located in 31 Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. The sample of the study was 800 teachers and 200 principals sampled through random sampling technique. The 800 teachers were used to assess the 200 principals in the study. The research questionnaire was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, Guidance and Counselling, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The reliability of the instrument was carried out by conducting a pilot study. Twenty teachers (who were not part of the study) were used to respond to the questionnaire. Data was retrieved from the instruments and test-retest method of

analysis was used to obtain data from the questionnaire. To test for the internal consistency Cronbach Alpha statistical measure was used. The reliability coefficient index score of 0.78 was obtained. The findings of the study revealed that the principals had ensured that new entrant teachers practiced their professional ethics to enhance their work but they did not ensure that teachers were mentored in their task areas for job enhancement. Based on the study findings, the researchers recommended that: the principals should continue to mentor new entrant teachers to practice their professional ethics to enhance their profession. These school heads should endeavour to make sure that they mentor teachers especially the neophytes in their task areas for them to be enhanced on the job.

Keywords: *Professional Ethics, Mentorship, School Leaders, New Entrant Teachers, Job Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The importance of secondary education has made it imminent that school leaders at this level of education should apply their expertise to ensure that teachers are well mentored. For these human resources to deliver the learning experiences as expected they do not only have to be qualified in their areas of specialty but they also have to keep their professional ethics and be well mentored in their task areas. A teacher who maintains the conduct of his profession will know the educational values and will keep the standard of teaching profession so as to achieve the stated objectives and the set goals. This teacher will create an environment where students can become active agents in the learning process to develop lifelong learning skills. Hence, they will maintain high standard or best practices in relation to students learning, planning, monitoring, assessing, reporting and providing feedback. He will according to Idasetima (2020) act in the best interest of students.

Teachers who are well mentored will have the right mind set, build more confidence in themselves and imbibe worthwhile behaviour towards the teaching profession. Obasi and Oke (2019) emphasized that mentoring will help an inexperienced teacher to ensure effective and quality education delivery. The researchers also maintained that mentoring will help the new entrant teachers to develop professional confidence

and competence through the mentors' professional skill and expertise. Mentoring of teachers will equip these teachers with effective teaching techniques, motivate and cause them to be dedicated to work. It has become very essential and crucial for the secondary schools' heads to ensure that effective mentoring of the teachers for efficiency and effectiveness in their task areas is carried out. One of the principals' major roles is to improve teachers' efficiency to achieve excellent teachers' job performance, that this can be attained through mentoring.

Concept Clarifications and Analysis

Professional Ethics

Professional ethics according to Omoh (2021) referred to the standard of human conduct sometimes called morals, which are acceptable rules and regulations, standard and quality control measure put in place to drive a certain profession. Mkonnen et al and Golga (2023) maintained that professional ethics is behaving according to the teaching principle which a professional teacher must adhere to. It also referred to the legal, ethical tenets, moral and rules guiding rights and wrongs capable of influencing the behaviours, ideas and attitude of teachers. The researchers further maintained that professional ethics include a teacher being honest, truthful, trustworthy, impartial, just, committed to work and using teaching resources effectively. Shapira- Lishchinsky (2020) stipulated that professional ethics is that teachers should have integrity, be honest, impartial in record assessment and balance with ethical responsibilities. Professional ethics are to enlighten the teachers on their major roles in bringing desirable changes in the behaviour of students, the ethics are designed to protect students' rights.

Mentorship/Mentoring

According to Omoh (2021) mentoring is a professional mentorship in which an experienced person (the mentor) assists an inexperienced person (a mentee) to develop specific knowledge and skills which will enhance the mentees personal and career growth. Pfund (2016) averred that mentoring is a collaborative learning relationship process that proceeds through purposeful stages over time as the mentor has a primary goal of helping the mentee acquire the essential competencies needed

for success in a chosen career. Professional ethics and mentorship in teaching have emphasized on teachers abiding on rules as stipulated in the Code of Professional Conduct established by the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) under Section 7(2)(6) of Act 2004. This code of professional conduct serves as an ethical compass to guide teachers' behavior or conduct in all ramifications of their professional capacity. It checks teacher's qualifications, knowledge, skill, competences, standard of teaching or professional responsibilities, values, relationships, integrity, conduct, practices, professional development, collegiality and collaboration. The teachers according to Jambarsang and Mehrparvar (2023) should be accountable to professional duties, attendance, timely assessment their teaching responsibility and should adhere to their professional values.

Teachers' professional values and relationships place emphasis on their developing a positive relationship with students, parents, colleagues, school management, school community and other school stakeholders. It also emphasized on teachers' professional integrity, that, they have to be honest, have integrity in all aspect of their work (Kirsi & Izuussisto 2022). They should have to avoid conflict between their professional work and private interest which if not checked could impact negatively on students. Their professional conduct should make them to ensure that they uphold the reputation of their profession, care for students under their surveillance or supervision, ensure their safety and welfare. They should work within the framework of relevant legislation and regulations. They should communicate effectively with students, colleagues, parents, school management, school community in a manner that is professional, collaborative and supportive, based on trust and respect. They should ensure not to teach under the influence of any substance which could impair their fitness to teach. On professional practices Omoh (2021) emphasized that teachers should:

- Maintain high ethical standards and practices in relation to teaching, students learning, planning, monitoring, assessing, reporting and providing feedback.
- Apply their knowledge and experiences to facilitate students' holistic development.

- Plan and communicate clear challenging and achievable expectations for students.
- Create an environment where students can become active agents in the learning process and in developing lifelong learning skills
- Balance between academic integrity, science literacy and respect for diverse beliefs.
- Use code of ethics proactively to support pedagogical decisions in contested Areas.
- Build healthy, respectful relationships with students and family.
- Develop teaching, learning and assessment strategies that support differentiated learning in a way that respects the dignity of all students.
- Inform their professional judgement and practice by engaging with and reflecting on students' development, learning theories, pedagogy, curriculum development, ethical practice, educational policy and legislation.
- In a context of mutual respect, they should be opened and responsive to constructive feedback regarding their practices and, if necessary, seek appropriate support, advice, guidance and act in the best interest of the students. On professional development the teachers should take personal responsibility for sustaining and improving the quality of their professional practices by:

Actively maintaining their professional knowledge and understanding, reflect and critically evaluate their professional practices, in light of their professional knowledge base. They should also avail themselves with the opportunities for career long professional development. For professional collegial collaboration, according to Omoh the principals should:

- Work with colleagues and students in the interest of sharing, developing, supporting good practice and maintaining the highest quality of best educational practices.
- Work in a collaborative manner with students, parents/guardians, school management, other members of staff, relevant professionals and the wider school community to effectively meet with students' needs.

- Cooperate with the inspectorate of the Department of Education and other statutory service and public non statutory educational and support services as appropriate
- Encourage professional self-regulation and contextual judgement rather than following bend rules
- Engage in the planning, implementation and evaluation of curriculum at classroom and school level (Foster & Maxwell, 2022, TRCN, Act 2001 cited in Idasetima 2020),

It is expected that when the school principals mentored teachers to adhere to all these professional ethics, these teachers would perform their jobs as expected. It is mandatory for the principals to use their professional expertise to properly mentor the new entrant teachers to be efficient and effective for enhancement of their jobs. The principals have to prepare their teachers through their necessary mentoring skills to effectively deliver pedagogical contents. Teachers should be mentored by the school principals to enable them effectively manage their students and be able to perform creditably well on their jobs Hayes and Mahfouz (2020). These school leaders should help inexperienced teachers through mentoring to have the content knowledge, understand how to break it down and adequately deliver it to learners for the expected learning outcomes to be achieved.

Principals must ensure that teachers have sufficient knowledge in their areas of study and must know how ideas connect contents of academic learning experience. This can support teachers' growth academically helping them to set and achieve their goals to daily life (Virella, 2022). Mentoring affords transferring of skills from experienced professionals to inexperienced teachers to apply in diverse professional circumstances. This will aid in promoting productive use of knowledge, in setting clear goals and roles, having career success, growth and job satisfaction. Fain and Zachary (2022) maintained that experienced individuals such as the school heads should through mentorship help the less experienced teachers to develop relationship with established professionals. These professionals should advise them on how to attain personal and career goals and should provide them with positive examples of ethical professional behaviour. Nyamori (2015) pointed out that school heads can

offer mentorship to new entrant teachers to help them manage challenges in the classrooms, overcome developmental task, fears, discouragement and anxieties. Mentoring at the secondary school level will help the new employees to acquire more knowledge, skills and technical know-how to effectively carry out their jobs and deliver instruction as expected. It will also enable these staff to be bold, have confidence to overcome anxiety and stress. Babatunde (2017) acknowledged that content knowledge is very important in teachers' classroom performance as it deals with teaching and learning process. Ekwenugo (2018) affirmed that mentoring is an inevitable tool to enhance teachers' effectiveness, that when teachers are properly mentored they offer their best.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers abiding by the rules, regulations and morals guiding their profession is paramount to help them to be focused, committed and serious in performing their duties. This can take place when their school heads who are experienced mentor them. It will help them to be knowledgeable in the curriculum content, pedagogical methods or styles of teachings. This will enable the teachers to be effective and possess required skills and competence to enhance their job performance. The emphasis is therefore placed on the school heads to ensure that they use their expertise to mentor the inexperienced teachers to have the technical know-how in instruction and other school activities so as to be effective to achieve stated objectives and goals. The problem of the present study lies on whether the principals has ensured that teachers observe their professional ethics and whether they have also mentored them in their task areas to be enhanced professionally. On the basis of the researchers are motivated to embark on the study "Professionals ethics and mentorship as correlates for school leaders enhancement of new-entrant teachers work performance in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Purpose

The objectives of this research papers are to:

1. Find out whether school principals have ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Investigate whether the principals have mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

Two research questions were set to guide the study:

1. Have principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?
2. Have principals mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Methodology

The researchers applied survey research design, to sample representative respondents from the population (Couper et al 2024). The population of the study was 3,378 teachers and 376 principals from public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (Secondary Education Board, 2020). Eight hundred (800) teachers and 200 principals were sampled through random sampling technique for the study. The 800 teachers were used to assess 200 principals. The research instrument was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Administration Foundation, Guidance and Counselling, Akwa Ibom State University. The reliability of the instrument was carried out by conducting a pilot study. Twenty teachers (who were not part of the study) responded to the questionnaire. Data was retrieved from the copies of the questionnaire after applying test-retest method, Cronbach alpha was used to measure the internal consistency of the instrument items. The reliability index score of 0.78 was obtained by Pearson Correlation coefficient and Spearman RHO Rank Order Correlation coefficient statistics. Mean statistics was used to analyse the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that: principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement but that the principals did not mentored teachers in their tasks areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommended

that: the principals should continue to mentor teachers to practise the ethics of their profession. They should endeavour to mentor the inexperienced teachers or should send them to consultants who are experts in mentorship for mentoring. This will help to enhance the teachers job performance.

Data Analysis

Research Question One: Have principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Principals ensuring that teachers practised their professional ethics

N=800

S/N	Indicators of Principals Ensuring that Teachers practised their Professional Ethics	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Decision
	Principals in your school ensure that you						
1	Are qualified to teach competently.	200	275	184	141	2.66	Agreed
2	Maintain cordial relationship with the stakeholders (the school management, colleagues, students and school community people).	250	280	177	93	2.86	Agreed
3	Monitor students to ensure their safety and welfare.	266	285	168	81	2.92	Agreed
4	Create a conducive environment for students' effective learning and development.	257	277	181	85	2.88	Agreed
5	Act in the best interest of students,, in all ramifications of their academic life.	340	279	179	2	3.20	Agreed
6	Develop professionally through training opportunities given to you.	268	288	182	62	2.95	Agreed

7	Work with other colleagues to maintain quality education practices.	270	268	178	84	2.90	Agreed
8	Work with the school management and students to provide students' needs.	120	90	286	304	2.03	Disagreed
9	Develop right pedagogy to teach.	260	277	159	104	2.86	Agreed
10	Apply your knowledge, skills and competence to help students to develop holistically	277	286	155	82	2.95	Agreed
	Sectional Mean					2.82	Accepted

The above table proved that the respondents with the mean scores of 2.67, 2.86, 2.92, 2.88, 3.20, 2.95, 2.91, 2.87 and 2.95 agreed that the principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement by making sure that they: were qualified to teach competently; maintained cordial relationship with their stakeholders (school management, colleagues, students and school community people), monitored students to ensure their safety and welfare; created a conducive environment for students' effective learning and development; act in the best interest of students, in all ramifications of their academic life; developed professionally through training opportunities given to you; worked with other colleagues to maintain quality education practices; developed the right pedagogy to teach and applied your knowledge, skills and competence to help students to develop holistically all led to your job embracement in your secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The respondents with the mean score of 2.03 disagreed that principals ensured that teachers work with the school management and students to provide students' needs in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. All the respondents with the sectional mean score of 2.82 accepted that the principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question Two: Have principals mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Principals mentoring teachers in their Task Areas for job enhancement

N=800

S/N	Indicators of Principals' Ensuring that Teachers are Mentored in their Task Areas for Job Enhancement	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Decision
	Principals in your schools have mentored you in your task areas for job enhancement, to:						
1	Effectively manage: the students to be studious in their studies.	100	90	260	350	1.93	Disagreed
2	Acquire the subject content knowledge to deliver instructions adequately for better student academic performance.	90	145	270	295	2.04	Disagreed
3	Help you to acquire professional skills for effective productivity.	80	60	297	363	1.82	Disagreed
4	State clear objectives and goals for better student academic achievement.	66	88	277	369	1.81	Disagreed
5	Attain personal and career goals.	70	99	289	342	1.87	Disagreed
6	Manage classroom challenges.	111	140	277	272	2.11	Disagreed
7	Overcome fear, discouragement and anxieties.	96	77	284	343	1.90	Disagreed
8	Solve students' developmental task problems.	85	135	288	292	2.02	Disagreed
9	Relate cordially with colleagues.	300	280	159	61	3.02	Agreed
10	Be enhanced professionally	270	285	168	77	2.94	Agreed
	Sectional Mean					2.15	Rejected

The above table revealed that the respondents with the mean scores of 1.93, 2.04, 1.82, 1.81, 1.87, 2.11, 1.91 and 2.02 disagreed that the principals have mentored teachers for job enhancement, to: effectively manage the students to be studious with their studies; acquire the subject content knowledge to deliver instructions adequately for better students' academic performance; help the teacher to acquire professional skills for effective productivity; state clear objectives and goals for

better student's academic achievement; attain personal and career goals; manage classroom challenges; overcome fear, discouragement and anxieties and solve students developmental task problems. The respondents with the means scores of 3.02 and 2.94 agreed that the principals have mentored teachers for job enhancement to: relate cordially with colleagues and be enhanced professionally. All the respondents with the sectional mean score of 2.1s5 rejected that principals have mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of question one proved that the principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Principals have ensured that: teachers are qualified to teach competently, maintain cordial relationship with their stakeholders (the school management, colleagues, students and school community people), monitor students to ensure their safety and welfare, create a conducive environment for students' effective learning and development, acts in the best interest of students, in all ramifications of their academic life, develop professionally through training opportunities given to them etcetera. Omoh (2021) study was in line with the finding of this study. The researcher advised that teachers should maintain high ethical standards and practices in relation to teaching, caring for students in all ramifications of their lives and that they should relate cordially with colleagues and the school management.

The finding of the research question two revealed that the principals did not mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. In the light of principals not mentoring the teachers in their task areas Zachary and Fain (2022) emphasized that experienced individuals such as the school heads should through mentorship help the less experienced teachers to apply professional ethics in all ramifications of their profession, especially that they should be committed in their task areas.

Conclusion

The researchers concluded based on the study findings that the principals ensured that teachers practised their professional ethics for job enhancement but that they did

not mentored teachers in their task areas for job enhancement in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the researchers recommended that principals should continue to encourage teachers to committedly practise the ethics of their profession. They should endeavour to mentor the inexperienced teachers, they should also consult consultants who are experts in mentorship to mentor teachers in their task areas, this will help to enhance the teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

References

1. Babatunde, M. M. (2017). Teaching practice exercise and classroom performance of ideal teachers in public secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 1(2), 49-53
2. Couper, A., Wagner, G., West B. T., Couper, M. P., Axinn, W. G., Wanger, J., Gatward, R., Saw, H-W., & Zhang, S. (2024). Toward a new approach to creating population - representative data for demographic research. *Demography*, 61(6), 1759-1791. <https://doi.-org/10.1215/00703370-11693878>
3. Ebuk, E. L., & Offiong, E.E. (2025). ETHICAL LEADERSHIP IN UTILIZING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT: CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD. *MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)*, 2(110), 01–17. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17317979>
4. EBUK, L. E., & CHUKWUEMEKA, E. J. (2025). EGOVERNANCE AND SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION: THE FUTURE OF EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP. *UAR Journal of Arts, Humanities & Social Sciences*, 1(7).
5. Ebuk, L. E., Abdullahi, A. A., & Chukwuemeka, E. J. (2025). ASSESSING PRINCIPALS' INVOLVEMENT IN YOUTH ICT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILL ACQUISITION FOR JOB CREATION IN

PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS, GWAGWALADA, ABUJA. *Nexus Global Research Journal of Multidisciplinary (NGRJM) 1(2) 66 – 75.*

6. Ebuk, E. L., & Chukwuemeka, E. J. (2023). Roles and Challenges of Academic Leaders in Students' Behavioural Modification for Enhancement of National Cohensiveness: A Study of the University of Abuja. *Journal of Contemporary Education Research.*
7. Ebuk, L. E., & Abdullahi, A. A. (2023). School leaders incorporating lifelong learning programme into educational system for student's transformation: Challenges and the way forward. *International Journal of Educational Research and Library Science, 12 (8), 75, 83.*
8. Ebuk, L. E., & Bankole, S. S. (2019). Principals' Supervisory Leadership Strategies and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in FCT, Abuja. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION (IJATE) Volume 11, No. 1 May, 2019, 133.*
9. Ebuk, L. E. (2019). Teachers utilization of improvement teaching strategies for instructional delivery in senior secondary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria. *SSAAR (JCER); Journal of Contemporary Education Research, 14(8), 196-203.*
10. Ebuk, L. E., Abdullahi, A. A.(2019). Issues and Prospects in the Administration of E-Learning in University Education in 21 st Century Nigeria. *Journal of Resourcefulness and Distinction, 17(1).*
11. Ebuk, L., & Bamijoko, O. (2016). The Effective Management of Mathematics Worktext: Sure Remedy to Students' Performance in Mathematics. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research, 3(5).*
12. Ekwenugo, A. B. (2018). Principals personal variables and teachers work behaviors in senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory. Unpublished Masters Dissertation submitted to the Department of Educational

Management, Faculty of Education, School of Postgraduate Studies, University of Abuja, Abuja.

13. Fain, L. Z. and Zachary, L. J. (2022). *The mentors Guide: Facilitating effective learning relationships* (3rd ed.), Hoboken, New Jersey, USA: Jossey-Bass/John Wiley & Sons.
14. Foster, D. S and Maxwell, B. (2022). Using codes of professional ethics and conduct in teacher education: Pitfalls and Best Practice in Ethics and integrity in Teacher Education. In S. E. Easten & Z.R.Khan (eds.) *Ethics and integrity in teacher education in teacher Education*, 25-42. Springer International Publishing.
15. Hayes, S. D. and Mahfouz J. (2020). Principalsip and mentoring: A review of perspectives evidence and literature. *Research in Educational Administration and Leadership*, 5(3), 722-751. <https://doi.org/0.30828/real/2020.4>
16. Idasetima, I. (2020). *Professionalization of Teaching of Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria for teachers' quality instruction and educational development: Challenges and prospects*. Unpublished Masters' Degree theses submitted to the Department of Educational Administration and Planning, School of Education, National Open University of Nigeria, Nigeria.
17. Ijuo, B. I., & Ebuk, L. E. (2020). Management refocusing on primary education for sustainability of peace and security in primary schools in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja, Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and social science, Sub-Sahara African Academic and Research Publications*, 17(6), 55-68.
18. Jambarsang, S. and Mehrparvar, A. H. (2023). Effective components of teachers' professionalism in viewpoints of various stakeholders. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*. e collection 2023. doi:10.4103/jehp-1565-21.
19. Kirsi, T. and Kuussisto E. (2022). *Teachers professional ethics*. Leiden/Boston: Brill (Open access),

20. Mkonnen, G. D. and Golga. D. N. (2023). Teachers' Ethical Professional Practices in higher education institutions: An instrumental case study, Education Annual. IntechOpen. Doing 10.57721/IntechOpen .109651.
21. Nyomori, S. (2015). The effect of workplace mentoring on employees' performance. A case study of SOS children's village (Master's project report). United States of America in International University-Africa.
22. Obasi, K. K. and Oke, E. B. (2019). Management administrative provisions for teacher mentoring in public secondary schools in Imo state, Nigeria. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications 9(2). www.ijsrp.org
23. Omoh, J. O. (2021) Influence of principals' mentorship on teachers work behavior in secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria. Unpublished Masters Dissertation submitted to the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, School of Postgraduate studies, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria.
24. Pfund, C. (2016). Studying the role and impact of mentoring on undergraduate research experience. Paper commissioned for the committee on strengthening research experiences for undergraduate STEM students. National Academic of Sciences, Teaching, Engineering and Medicine available: http://nas.edu/STEM_undergraduate_research_mentoring
25. Shapira-Lishchinsky, O. (2020). A multidimensional study of teachers codes of ethics attitudes of educational leaders. NASSP Bulletin, 104(1), 5-9. <https://doi.org/10.1117/0192636520907694> Professional ethics, Leiden/Boston: Brill (open access)
26. Shajobi-Ibikunle, G., & Oluwadamilola, S. O. D. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and Corporate Criminality: Emerging Challenges in Liability and Accountability. Law and Social Justice Review, 5(3).

27. Shajobi-Ibikunle, D. G., & Kassim, R. M. (2023). Domestic violence: a critical review of the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act (VAPP) 2015. *Encyclopedia of Domestic Violence*, 1-11.
28. Shajobi-Ibikunle, G., & Oluwadamilola, S. O. D. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and Corporate Criminality: Emerging Challenges in Liability and Accountability. *Law and Social Justice Review*, 5(3).
29. Shajobi-Ibikunle, G., & Oseghale, D. O. S. (2025). A RE-EXAMINATION OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROTECTION OF SHAREHOLDERS' RIGHTS IN NIGERIA. *LexScriptio A Journal of the Department of Jurisprudence and Public Law*, 2(2), 1-27.
30. Shajobi-Ibikunle, G., & Shajobi-Oseghale, D. O. (2025). Legal Regime of Corporate Governance and Shareholders' Rights in Nigeria. *Journal of Commercial and Property Law*, 12(1), 156-165.
31. Virella, P. M. and Cobb, C. (2022). Leader developer: Perspectives of mentor principals in an administrator preparation program *Journal of Educational Supervision*, 5(3), 81-99. <https://doi.org/10.31045/jes.5.3.4>